

The Influence of The Talking Stick Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes Theme 2 Unity in Difference Class VI SDN 091607 Sinaksak

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A R Q I C L E I N F O

ABSTRACT

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This Research Aims To Determine The Influence Of The Talking Stick Learning Model On Student Learning Outcomes Theme 2 Unity In Difference Class Vi State 091607 Sinaksak Primary School, The method in this research is a quantitative experimental type method whose research design form is pre-experimental type one group pretest-posttest. The population and sample used were saturated sampling with 24 samples, as well as two research variables: the dependent variable (x) in the form of learning outcomes, and the independent variable (y) in the form of the talking stick model. The data collection technique is the test technique. Test results using the t-test technique with the help of the spss program, based on the results of calculating the significant value (2-tailed) < 0.05 , namely $0.000 < 0.05$, $t_{count} > t_{table} = 22.859 > 2.064$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the *Talking stick learning model* on the learning outcomes of class VI students in theme 2 unity in differences subtheme 1 harmony in differences in class VI SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the most important human needs, which is able to enable humans to continue to develop and compete in the life of society, nation and state. The educational process aims to develop student potential, not just transfer knowledge. Students must be viewed as organisms that are developing and have potential. So teachers must be able to develop students' potential optimally, by providing broad insight, providing creative opportunities and providing support.

One of the levels of education provided by the Indonesian government is elementary school. Elementary schools (SD) as basic educational institutions aim to prepare students to face future life by developing their potential. In its implementation, learning that takes place in schools still faces various problems, including the lack of students' ability to understand the learning being delivered. Learning success is determined and influenced by several aspects including students' basic abilities, students' learning motivation, and the learning model used by teachers in class.

A good learning process is a learning process that allows students to actively involve themselves in the whole, both mentally and physically. The teacher as an educator has the duty to carry out the teaching and learning process. Teachers must have models so that the teaching and learning process can take place optimally. The use of models in teaching and learning activities is very necessary to facilitate the learning process. Without a clear model, the learning process will not be directed so that the learning objectives that have been set will not take place effectively and efficiently.

That the learning process still tends to be passive when the teacher explains the learning material, there are still many students who do not pay attention to the teacher, such as talking to friends, are sleepy during learning and there are still teachers who do not use a variety of models. This results in students not understanding the material presented by the teacher. Apart from that, there is a lack of students' desire to ask questions, students still feel less confident in expressing opinions, there is a lack of communication with teachers and friends, and student learning outcomes are still relatively low.

Thematic subjects, Indonesian Language (BI) subject content, information was obtained that the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) in this subject was 70. Based on the daily test scores of students in class VI of SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak, there were 10 students whose scores were above the KKM. (Passed) and 14 students whose scores were below the KKM (did not pass). This shows that the learning outcomes achieved by students are still low. And in the Social Sciences (IPS) subject content, information was obtained that the Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM) in this subject was 70. Based on the daily test scores of students in class VI of SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak, there were 9 students whose scores were above the KKM (passed) and 15 students whose scores were below the KKM (did not pass). This shows that the learning outcomes achieved by students.

The learning model that can be applied is the Talking Stick learning model, which is one of the cooperative learning models. This learning strategy is carried out using the help of a stick, whoever holds the stick is obliged to answer the teacher's questions after the students have studied the main material. According to Gunardi (2023:15), talking stick learning is very suitable for elementary school students. Apart from practicing speaking, this learning will create a pleasant atmosphere and make students active.

According to Oktavia (2018:87) Talking Stick learning is a learning model that can encourage students to dare to express opinions. It is hoped that the use of the Talking Stick learning model will be able to foster high levels of interaction between teachers and students or between students. And makes students more enthusiastic, motivated

and the learning process becomes more enjoyable. Ultimately it will improve student learning outcomes.

Based on the background of this problem, the researcher conducted research with the title "The Influence of the Talking Stick Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes Theme 2 Unity in Differences Subtheme 1 Harmony in Differences Class VI SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework is the process of answering the problem formulation based on the theory being tested, namely the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The conceptual framework aims to provide an overview of the basic concepts used in research so that it can show the way of thinking appropriately while being able to accommodate all existing problems by solving the problems.

Thus, in order to successfully achieve the desired learning objectives, an appropriate learning model is needed to support the success of these learning objectives, namely the Talking Stick learning model. The Talking Stick learning model is a teacher learning process that connects the teaching materials provided with sticks/tools. In this Talking Stick learning model, the focus is on learning more effectively and being brave enough to express opinions. In this case, students must understand the meaning of learning, what the benefits are and how to achieve it. Students will study with more enthusiasm and attention because they know that what they learn will be useful in the future. Therefore, it can be assumed that there is a significant influence through the influence of the Talking Stick learning model on learning outcomes in theme 2 Unity in Differences sub-theme 1 Harmony in Differences at SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

METHOD

The research used is quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2021), quantitative methods are called traditional methods, because this method has been used for a long time so it has become a tradition as a method for research. This method is also called a positivistic method because it is based on the philosophy of positivism. The type of research used is experimental research, namely the Pre-Experimental type. Sugiyono (2021) said that pre-experimental design is a design that includes only one group or class

that is given pre- and post-tests. This one group pretest and posttest design was carried out on one group without a control or comparison group. With this research, the results of the treatment can be known more accurately, because it can be compared with the situation before treatment and after treatment.

Table 1 one Group Pretest-posttest design

O₁	X	O₂
Pre-test	Treatment	Posttest

Information:

O₁ = Initial test (*pretest*) before using the *talking stick model*

X = *Talking stick model treatment*

O₂ = Final test (*posttest*) after using the *talking stick model*

The population in the research were all students at VI SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak, totaling 24 students. This research uses a test instrument in the form of multiple choices with the aim of measuring learning outcomes. Before it is used for data collection, the data testing stage uses validity testing, reliability testing, difficulty level testing, and differentiating data testing. In data analysis, the normality test, homogeneity test, t-test were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

This research was carried out in Class IV of SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak Jln. Medan Km 10 GG Cambodia, Simalungun, Siantar District, Simalungun Regency, North Sumatra from 05 October 2023 to 19 October 2023. This research was conducted to find out how much influence the Talking Stick Model has *on* student learning outcomes.

This research is a *pre-experimental design research with a one group pretest posttest design*. Where students are given a *pretest* and *posttest*. The *pretest* is given before treatment, the aim is to determine the initial condition of the students before being given treatment. The *posttest* is given after the learning material is given using the *Talking Stick Model*, the aim is to find out the final condition of the students given the treatment.

Instrument Test

1. Validity Test

A measure that shows the levels of validity of an instrument. For validity, it is carried out using SPSS Version 25, a question item is said to be valid if the calculated r value is > r table, with a significance level of 5% or 0.05. In determining the r table, you can look at the r product moment table. It can be seen that there are 20 valid questions (question 7, question 8, question 9, question 10, question 11, question 12, question 13, question 14, question 15, question 16, question 17, question 18, question 19, question 21, question 22, question 24, question 26, question 27, question 28 and question 30) while 10 questions were declared invalid (question 1, question 2, question 3, question 4, question 5, question 6, question 20, question 23, question 25 and question 29)

2. Reliability Test

The Cronbach's Alpha value obtained was 0.84 Next, this value is compared with the reliability coefficient criteria, namely if the Cronbach's Alpha value is > 0.7 then the question is said to be reliable, so it can be concluded that 0.84 > 0.7, so the questions on this test instrument are very reliable.

3. Test the level of difficulty

Shows that the 20 questions that were tested were classified as easy, with 5 questions, namely (question 1, question 3, question 6, question 20, question 27, questions with a medium level of difficulty, 20 questions, namely (question 2, question 4), question 5, question 9, question 10, question 11, question 13, question 14, question 15,

question 16, question 17, question 18, question 19, question 23, question 24, question 25, question 26, question 29, question 30) and 5 questions with a difficult level of difficulty, namely (question 7, question 8, question 21, question 22, question 28).

4. Differentiating Power Test

There are 11 questions categorized as good, namely (question 7, question 8, question 12, question 13, question 14, question 15, question 16, question 19, question 26, question 27, question 28), categorized as Good, there is question 11, namely (question 5, question 9, question 10, question 11, question 17, question 18, question 21, question 22, question 24, question 29, question 30). In the Bad category there is question 7, namely (Question 2, Question 3, Question 4, Question 6, Question 20, Question 23, Question 25), in the Very Bad category there is Question 1, namely (Question 1)

DATA ANALYSIS

1. Normality Test

The Normality Test is carried out to determine whether the Pretest and Posttest data from the sample is normally distributed or not. Normality test results using the Kolmogrov-Smimov method in the SPSS Version 25 program obtained the following data:

Table 2 Normality Test

Tests of Normality							
	Kelas	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Hasil	Pretest	.150	24	.176	.939	24	.152
	Posttest	.168	24	.079	.941	24	.169
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction							

Based on table 4.9, it can be seen that the *Pretest* value > from the significant value, namely $0.17 > 0.05$, meaning the *pretest data* is normal. And a value of $0.79 > 0.05$ means that *the Posttest* is normal.

2. Homogeneity Test

The Homogeneity Test is used to determine whether several population data variants are the same or not. The test was carried out with the help of SPSS version 25 For Windows. With the criteria, testing if the significance value is > 0.05 then it can be said that the variance of the two data is the same. The following homogeneity test results can be seen in the following table.

Table 3 Homogeneity Test

Test of Homogeneity of Variances					
		Levene Statistics	df1	df2	Sig.
Hasil	Based on Mean	.179	1	46	.674
	Based on Median	.209	1	46	.650

Based on Median and with adjusted df	.209	1	45.949	.650
Based on trimmed mean	.173	1	46	.679

Based on the results of the homogeneity test above, it can be seen that the significance value for the Homogeneity test is 0.67. The significance criterion is > 0.05 , so it can be concluded that the pretest and posttest scores have the same homogeneous variance

3. T test (Hypothesis)

Hypothesis testing was carried out to determine the effect of the *Talking Stick learning model* on student learning outcomes theme 2 unity in differences subtheme 1 harmony in differences in class VI SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak

Table 4 Hypothesis Test Results

Paired Samples Test		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pair	Hasil - Kelas	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
1		66,521	20,161	2,910	60,667	72,375	22,859	47	,000

Based on the table above, the significant value (2-tailed) < 0.05 , namely $0.000 < 0.05$, $t_{count} > t_{table} = 22.859 > 2.064$ then it is rejected and accepted. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the *Talking stick learning model* on the learning outcomes of class VI students in theme 2 unity in differences subtheme 1 harmony in differences in class VI SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak

Discussion

This research was carried out in class VI of SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak for the 2023/2024 academic year from 12 October - 24 October 2023. The population used was all students of class VI of SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak with a sample of class VI students of 24 students. This section will explain results found in research that has been carried out. The intended results are conclusions drawn based on the data collected and data analysis that has been carried out. This research aims to determine the influence of the Talking Stick Learning Model on Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Unity in Differences Subtheme 1 Harmony in Differences in class VI of SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak for the 2023/2024 academic year which has 24 students in this research. Before carrying out the research, the research first carried out a trial of the instrument at the same level with a different school, namely at SD Negeri 091425 Boluk. This trial was carried out in order to

determine the number of questions out of 30 questions that would be tested in multiple choice form, namely 20 questions.

Based on the Pretest results, the average student learning outcome score was 50.41 with all students scoring below the KKM. Looking at the existing percentages, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using the Problem Based Talking Stick Model was relatively low. Furthermore, the average value of the Posttest results is 85.83. So after using the Talking Stick Learning Model, students have better learning outcomes than before using the Talking Stick Learning Model. After the Pretest and Posttest Normality tests were carried out, the Homogeneity test was carried out. Based on the Homogeneity test, a significant value of 0.674 was obtained. Based on predetermined criteria, if the sig value is > 0.05 , the data is said to have homogeneous variation. In this case it can be seen that $0.674 > 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the data has the same characteristics or is homogeneous. the influence of the Talking Stick Learning Model on the learning outcomes of class VI students at SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak for the 2023/2024 academic year. 05. From the data obtained, the alternative hypothesis is accepted, namely that there is an influence of the Talking Stick learning model on the learning outcomes of class VI students at SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak for the 2023/2024 academic year.

This research is also supported by previous research conducted by Lisbet et al (2022). The influence of the Talking Stick learning model on student learning outcomes in theme 2 sub-theme 1 learning 1 class III of SD Negeri 096768 Tambun Marisi Kec.dolog Masagal Kab.Simalungun obtained an increase in results learning was 29 with an average pretest score = 56.25 and an average posttest score = 85.25. Meanwhile in the control class (IIIB) an increase in learning outcomes was obtained by 27.25 with an average pretest score = 60 and posttest= 77, 25. This means that the average learning outcomes of the experimental class using the talking stick learning model are better than the average learning outcomes of control class students using the conventional learning model.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of the research data, researchers can conclude that the *Talking Stick learning model is used* has a significant effect on the learning outcomes of class VI students at SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak for the 2023/2024 academic year. This can be proven by the research results which include the pretest results of students in class V which have an average score of 50.41 and the posttest results of students in class VI which have an average score of 85.83. With the hypothesis results in the paired sample t test which is has been carried out, the obtained value of sig(2-tailed) < 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) and $t_{count} > t_{table} = 22,859 > 2, 064$ So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the learning model *Talking Stick* on student learning outcomes in theme 2 unity in differences, subtheme 1 harmony in differences, class VI SD Negeri 091607 Sinaksak FY 2023/2024 , so the hypothesis in this research is accepted.

Recommendations

Based on this research, the researcher provides suggestions according to the results of the research that has been carried out as follows:

- a. For teachers, teachers should use learning models that are appropriate to the material being taught so that students are more active and motivated in learning activities and can improve student learning outcomes.
- b. So that students are more active during the learning process, the teacher acts as a facilitator who encourages students to carry out learning activities. Teachers position themselves as guides in the course of learning discussions so that students are more active in learning.
- c. Researchers can apply the model in this research as an effort to improve student learning outcomes when they become teachers
- d. For students with research regarding the influence of learning models *Talking Stick* learning outcomes can provide knowledge and information that can be used during teaching practice.

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